

Environmental data preparation

Deliverable 2.1

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List of acronyms and abbreviations

Acronym/Abbreviation	Meaning/Full text
FAIR	Findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable
MPA	Marine protected areas
WP	Work package

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The MPA Europe project

MPA Europe is a project co-funded by the European Union (EU) that will map a network of locations representative of biodiversity in European seas (Atlantic Exclusive Economic Zones of the EU and its neighbours, and all the Mediterranean, Baltic, and Black seas) (Figure 1).

Figure 1: MPA Europe study area.

This network will indicate where to prioritise placement of Marine Protected Areas (MPA) for biodiversity protection and how Maritime Spatial Planning (MSP) can maximise blue carbon benefits. By using a holistic set of biodiversity measures, from species to ecosystems (including habitats), and environmental data including carbon storage, water currents, and climate change velocity models, it will be possible to quantify and map both the present and future connectivity within the proposed MPA network. The multiple scenarios provided will support wider and improved MSP by policy makers, industry, non-governmental organizations (NGOs), and European regional seas organisations with identification of further potential areas for cross-border MPA. The major scientific areas of the project and its outcomes are summarized in the infographic presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2. MPA Europe project scientific areas

The inter-disciplinary approach of MPA Europe is supported by a diversity of partners. These include Nord University (Norway), the Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission of UNESCO (Belgium), the Scottish Association for Marine Science (Scotland, UK), the Centre of Marine Sciences (Portugal), the Ocean University of China (China), Science Crunchers (Portugal), the University of the Ryukyus (Japan), Aarhus University (Denmark), and the Joint Nature Conservation Committee (England, UK). The partners include experts in marine biology, taxonomy, ecology, oceanography, biogeochemistry, and biogeography, MPA network design, benthic habitat mapping, carbon dynamics, species distribution, climate modelling, and MSP compose the MPA Europe team.

1. Deliverable 2.1 Overview

The present document reports the Deliverable 2.1 of MPA Europe. This serves as a comprehensive data descriptor, detailing the data acquisition sources, standardized frameworks used, and computational procedures involved in generating spatially complete and standardized environmental data layers for European Seas. These data are crucial for policy-relevant research focusing on MPA designation, in particular, mapping of biodiversity patterns, and quantifying biodiversity impacts under global change scenarios.

The environmental data layers will feed three main tasks of MPA Europe:

Ecosystems (WP2):

The task focuses on the first-ever classification of marine ecosystems in Europe, spanning from the surface to the seafloor. The classification is driven by **spatially complete and standardized environmental data** that accurately reflect both the conditions and functioning of ecosystems.

Climate velocity (WP2):

The task will use **spatially complete and standardized environmental data** to assess the velocity of climate change, which combines spatial gradients and temporal trends in temperature to map areas with fast and slow climate velocities.

Species (WP3):

The task will use **spatially complete and standardized environmental data** in well-established "environmental niche modelling" methods, including state-of-the-art ensemble modelling of multiple algorithms, to produce range maps for various species.

2. Methods

Spatially complete and standardized environmental data layers for the European seas were developed using the state-of-the-art computational pipelines of Bio-ORACLE (Assis *et al.*, 2017). This facilitated the delivery of a comprehensive dataset comprising numerous ecologically meaningful layers.

Data layers were generated at a 0.05° resolution (approx. 5 km at the equator), per decade, for present-day conditions (period 2000 to 2020) and for the span of the Shared Socioeconomic Pathway (SSP) scenarios (Riahi *et al.*, 2017) of future climate change (period 2030 to 2100), ranging from (1) a "sustainability" scenario SSP1-1.9 following the target of Paris Agreement of reduced greenhouse gas emissions, to (2) the "fossil-fuelled development" SSP5-8.5 scenario of high emissions and low challenges to adaptation (Table 1). Raw data for present-day conditions (period 2000 to 2020) were acquired at the monthly basis from Global Ocean Physics Analysis and Forecast and the Global Ocean Biogeochemistry Analysis and Forecast, two pre-processed re-analyses of Copernicus Marine Service that integrate and assimilate a comprehensive range of satellite and in-situ data. Data for the span of Shared Socioeconomic Pathway scenarios of future climate change (period 2020 to 2100) were acquired at the monthly basis from numerous Atmosphere-Ocean General

Circulation Models (AOGCMs) provided by the 6th phase of Coupled Model Intercomparison Project (CMIP), namely:

- ACCESS-ESM1-5 (Australian Community Climate and Earth System Simulator - Earth System Model 1.5),
- CanESM5 (Canadian Earth System Model 5),
- CESM2-WACCM (Community Earth System Model 2 – Whole Atmosphere Community Climate Model),
- CNRM-ESM2-1 (Centre National de Recherches Météorologiques - Earth System Model 2.1),
- GFDL-ESM4 (Geophysical Fluid Dynamics Laboratory - Earth System Model 4),
- GISS-E2-1-G (Goddard Institute for Space Studies – Model E 2.1G),
- IPSL-CM6A-LR (Institut Pierre Simon Laplace – Climate Model Phase 6A-Low Resolution),
- MIROC-ES2L (Model for Interdisciplinary Research on Climate - Earth System version 2 Long-term simulations),
- MPI-ESM1-2-LR (Max Plank Institute – Earth System Model 1.2 – Low Resolution),
- MRI-ESM2-0 (Meteorological Research Institute – Earth System Model 2.0),
- and UKESM1-0-LL (United Kingdom Earth System Model 1.0 – Low Resolution).

To facilitate ecological modelling, six predictors per variable were produced. These predictors included the long-term average, minimum and maximum records, long-term average of the minimum and maximum records per year (e.g., temperature of the warmest month on average), and range.

Table 1. Summary of Shared Socioeconomic Pathway (SSP) narratives.

Scenario	Narrative
SSP1	The world is gradually but steadily evolving toward a more sustainable path, emphasizing more inclusive growth that considers perceived ecological restrictions. The global commons are progressively being managed better, educational and health investments are hastening the demographic transition, and the emphasis shifts away from economic growth and toward a broader focus on human well-being. As a result of an increasing commitment to achieving development goals, inequality is diminishing both across and within countries. Consumption is aimed at achieving minimal material growth as well as low resource and energy intensity.
SSP2	The world is advancing in a direction where social, economic, and technological inclinations do not deviate greatly from historical patterns. Development and income development are proceeding unevenly, with some countries making reasonable progress and others falling short of expectations. Global and national institutions work together to achieve long-term development goals, but progress is slow. Despite certain gains, environmental systems deteriorate, and the intensity of resource and energy use decreases overall. Global population growth is predicted to be modest and gradual in the second half of the twentieth century. Income disparities continue or improve gradually, and reducing vulnerability to societal changes remains difficult.
SSP3	Resurgent nationalism, competition and security concerns, and regional conflicts all force governments to emphasize internal or, at best, regional issues. Over time, policies become more focused on national and regional security concerns. Countries prioritize achieving regional energy and food security goals over broad-based development. Investment in education and technological development is decreasing. Economic development is slow, consumer spending is materialistic, and inequities persist or worsen over time. Population increase in affluent countries is moderate, while it is rapid in underdeveloped countries. Environmental degradation is exacerbated in some areas due to a low global priority for addressing environmental issues.

SSP4	High discrepancies in human capital investment, combined with expanding disparities in economic opportunity and political influence, contribute to increased inequities and stratification within and between countries. The chasm between a globally connected civilization that contributes to knowledge- and capital-intensive sectors of the global economy and a fragmented collection of lower-income, less educated cultures operating in a labor-intensive, low-tech economy widens with time. Social cohesion deteriorates, and conflict and instability proliferate. The high-tech economy and sectors are seeing fast technological advancement. The global energy market is diversifying, with investments in both carbon-intensive fuels like coal and unconventional oil and low-carbon energy alternatives.
SSP5	This world is increasingly convinced that competitive markets, innovation, and participatory societies will result in rapid technological advancement and human capital development as the path to long-term development. Global markets are increasingly linked. Furthermore, considerable expenditures in health, education, and institutions are being made to develop human and social capital. Simultaneously, the worldwide push for economic and social progress is accompanied by the extraction of vast amounts of fossil fuel resources and the adoption of resource- and energy-intensive lifestyles. All of these factors lead to high global economic growth, even when global population peaks and decreases in the twenty-first century.

The reliability of the data layers was assessed by cross-validating the outputs with in situ quality-controlled data provided by the Global Ocean Data Analysis Project (GLODAP) (Lauvset *et al.*, 2021). This cross-validation process focused on temperature, salinity, phosphate, nitrate, silicate, dissolved oxygen, and chlorophyll (Assis *et al.*, 2017) and involved comparing the downscaled outputs of the raw data used to generate the predictor variables with the actual data available in the GLODAP dataset at the corresponding geographic positions and depths of each sample. Several statistical analyses, including mean absolute error, root mean square error, and Pearson's correlation, were employed to examine the relationship between the interpolated and in situ data.

3. Environmental data

We produced a comprehensive collection of ecologically relevant environmental data layers (Table 2), specifically designed for bioclimatic modelling. These data are provided for the surface and benthic realms, for both present-day conditions and the new generation of climate change SSP scenarios. Specifically, these data include 6 predictors for the key variables temperature, salinity, sea ice cover, sea ice thickness, sea water velocity, mixed layer depth, diffuse attenuation coefficient, photosynthetically available radiation (PAR), PAR at bottom, oxygen, pH, iron, phosphate, nitrate, silicate, primary production (total phytoplankton), chlorophyll, topographic (slope) and topographic (roughness).

Additional layers of bathymetry, sedimentation rates, seabed substrates, distance to coast and distance to closest port were acquired from the European Marine Observation and Data Network (EMODnet) and Marine Spatial Ecology (MARSPEC) (Sbrocco & Barber, 2013).

Table 2. Comprehensive collection of ecologically relevant environmental data layers.

Variable	Ref. system	Extent coverage	Temporal coverage	File format
Temperature	WGS84	NA, MS, BIS, BaS and RS	2000-2100, decadal	Raster
Salinity	WGS84	NA, MS, BIS, BaS and RS	2000-2100, decadal	Raster
Sea Ice Cover	WGS84	NA, MS, BIS, BaS and RS	2000-2100, decadal	Raster
Sea Ice Thickness	WGS84	NA, MS, BIS, BaS and RS	2000-2100, decadal	Raster
Sea Water Velocity	WGS84	NA, MS, BIS, BaS and RS	2000-2100, decadal	Raster
Mixed Layer Depth	WGS84	NA, MS, BIS, BaS and RS	2000-2100, decadal	Raster
Diffuse Attenuation Coefficient	WGS84	NA, MS, BIS, BaS and RS	2000-2020, decadal	Raster
PAR	WGS84	NA, MS, BIS, BaS and RS	2000-2020, decadal	Raster
PAR at bottom	WGS84	NA, MS, BIS, BaS and RS	2000-2020, decadal	Raster
Oxygen	WGS84	NA, MS, BIS, BaS and RS	2000-2100, decadal	Raster
pH	WGS84	NA, MS, BIS, BaS and RS	2000-2100, decadal	Raster
Iron	WGS84	NA, MS, BIS, BaS and RS	2000-2100, decadal	Raster
Phosphate	WGS84	NA, MS, BIS, BaS and RS	2000-2100, decadal	Raster
Nitrate	WGS84	NA, MS, BIS, BaS and RS	2000-2100, decadal	Raster
Silicate	WGS84	NA, MS, BIS, BaS and RS	2000-2100, decadal	Raster
Total phytoplankton	WGS84	NA, MS, BIS, BaS and RS	2000-2100, decadal	Raster
Chlorophyll	WGS84	NA, MS, BIS, BaS and RS	2000-2100, decadal	Raster
Topographic (slope)	WGS84	NA, MS, BIS, BaS and RS	-	Raster
Topographic (roughness)	WGS84	NA, MS, BIS, BaS and RS	-	Raster
EMODnet Bathymetry	WGS84	NA, MS, BIS, BaS and RS	-	Raster
Sedimentation Rates	WGS84	NA, MS, BIS, BaS and RS	-	Raster
Seabed Substrates	WGS84	NA, MS, BIS, BaS and RS	-	Raster
Distance to coast	WGS84	NA, MS, BIS, BaS and RS	-	Raster
Distance to closest port	WGS84	NA, MS, BIS, BaS and RS	-	Raster

NA: North Atlantic Ocean; MS: Mediterranean Sea; BIS: Black Sea; BaS: Baltic Sea; RS: Red Sea

The cross-validation testing the reliability of the data layers, which included the statistics of mean absolute error, root mean square error, and Pearson's correlation, revealed a strong paired relationship between the interpolated and in situ data. Overall, the layers mirror the climatic patterns observed in the quality-controlled data, as evidenced by the low error rates and high correlation coefficients obtained for all variables (Table 3).

Table 3. Accuracy assessed with quality-control data.

Variable	MAE	RMSE	Cor	n
Temperature	0.096	0.934	0.996	70802
Salinity	0.045	0.685	0.937	71442
Oxygen	0.051	18.102	0.963	46596
Silicate	2.795	10.177	0.860	45186
Phosphate	0.062	0.215	0.937	42838
Nitrate	0.650	2.876	0.939	45083

MAE: mean average error; RMSE: root mean square error; Cor: Pearson's correlation coefficient; n: number of quality-control records.

Present-day sea surface temperature

Future (decade 2090) sea surface temperature

Present-day seafloor temperature

Future (decade 2090) seafloor temperature

Figure 3. Example of the data layers produced for the European Seas. Colour gradients reflect spatial differences in environmental conditions. Dashed area depicts MPA Europe study area.

The collection of environmental data layers is provided under the FAIR principle (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability) in a user-friendly format (GeoTIFF- files), under a standardized grid system covering the European seas. The layers were tailored to facilitate seamless integration and analysis across different regions and scales, enhancing the efficiency and accuracy of bioclimatic modelling efforts of WP2 and WP3.

The report represents the most up to date status of the information. Any potential upcoming information may be considered for incorporation in future deliverables to improve the scientific knowledge.

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